

Small Bowel Perforation: A Clinical Investigation and Management Program in A Teaching Hospital for Tertiary Care

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Abstract:

Background: In the current research region, small bowel perforations are among the most frequent surgical abdominal emergencies seen. Their delayed manifestation presents a challenge for diagnosis and therapy. The current study was out to ascertain the etiological causes, clinical characteristics, age, sex, incidence, and different surgical techniques for small Bowel perforations and the associated setup problems.

Methods: From October 2023 to January 2024, 100 cases were observed prospectively in a single educational institution as part of this investigation. Numerous pieces of information were examined, tallied, and assessed, including the patient's presentation, age and sex incidence, etiologies, pathological aspects, morbidity, and mortality related to the cause and treatment. Through data analysis, frequent causes of small bowel perforations, the best modality for investigation and treatment, complications related to various management strategies, and potential preventative measures were examined.

Findings: all small bowel perforations, duodenal perforations accounted for 68 % of cases. These were followed by ileal (23%) and jejunal (7%). Typhoid fever (47.8%) was the most common cause of ileal perforation, followed by TB (13%) and trauma (13%). Total death rate from minor bowel perforations was 15%, and the mortality rate from ileal perforation (39%) was higher than that from duodenal perforation (8.5%). Common side effects were wound infection, toxemia, uraemia, hypotension, and respiratory issues; these were more frequently observed in ileal perforation cases.

Conclusions: The study demonstrated that improved results in these instances were attained by efficient pre-surgical management, including sufficient fluid resuscitation, prompt operative intervention, and appropriate post-operative care. Hence, the best course of action for patients with small intestinal perforations is early identification and effective treatment.

Keywords: Complications mortality, Management, Perforation, Small bowel, Typhoid perforation.

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Introduction

In India, perforation peritonitis is the most frequent surgical emergency. Since the majority of peritonitis cases (75.55% and 70.8%) are caused by small intestinal perforation, surgeons treating these cases should be aware of the numerous risks of small bowel perforation. [1,2]

The spectrum differs significantly from the west [2]. The death as a result of Small intestinal perforation rates is still high, ranging from 11.5% to 37% in different studies, and early detection is crucial in these cases. [3]. Thus, it becomes essential that we comprehend their various etiologies, manifestations, and administration in great detail.

Perforations in the small bowel were and continue to be a great challenge for surgeon's despite of the better understanding of pathophysiology, advances in diagnosis, surgery, antimicrobial therapy and intensive care support. This study aims to study the various etiologies, incidence rates, clinical presentations and surgical outcomes of small bowel perforations.

Methods

A prospective study was conducted at Victoria Hospital in Bangalore, India, involving one hundred patients who received surgical intervention for peritonitis resulting from small intestinal perforation between October 2023 and January 2024. Patients who weren't 12 years old were not

allowed. A clinical assessment using simple X-rays or CT scans was used to make the decision to perform surgery, which would be done at the surgeon's discretion. Pre-operative parenteral antibiotics and adequate fluid resuscitation were administered. There was also continuous decompression with a nasogastric tube. Every patient had an exploratory laparotomy, and the surgeon's operative assessment alone determined the kind of operational care to be used.

Every intestinal anastomosis was stitched by hand. A thorough peritoneal wash was administered, and two drains—one at the perforation site and one in the pelvis—were inserted beforehand. Until its conclusion. Following surgery, the patients were sent to the post-operative ward, where they were attentively observed. Based on the perioperative circumstances, the surgeon and anesthetist jointly decided whether or not postoperative ICU admission was necessary. Age, gender, concomitant diseases, presenting signs and symptoms, and clinical characteristics were among the information gathered. The normal preoperative blood work-up's laboratory results were also noted. Patients had USG scans of the abdomen and pelvis as part of their standard pre-operative evaluation. In

every case where perforations owing to typhoid were suspected, a Widal test was performed. HPE surrounding the ulcer margin. Whenever necessary, the edge or any questionable lymph nodes were examined. Furthermore, the reason for the perforation, the surgical results and treatments, additionally recorded were the length of hospital stay, death, and perioperative complications. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to analyze the data that was gathered.

Results

This study involved one hundred patients, of whom ninety were male and the remaining ten were female. The patients ranged in age from 16 to 62. The majority of age group. The age range that was most frequently impacted was 31 to 40. Table 1 displays the distribution by age and gender.

With 95% of the patients being the only earner in the home and the majority coming from low socioeconomic backgrounds, the patients and their families suffered grave financial and psychological consequences. Seventy-two patients had hemoglobin levels less than 11 grams per milliliter, and 67 of them had BMIs below 20 kg/m², indicating general dietary deficiencies.

Table 1: Gender and age distribution of study cases

Age/Years	Male		Female		Total	
12-20	4	5.7	3	30	7	7
21-30	30	42.8	4	40	34	34
31-40	40	57.1	2	20	42	42
41-50	9	12.8	1	10	10	10
>50	7	10	0	0	7	7
Total	90	100	10	100	100	100

All 100 instances had abdominal pain at the outset. Sixty-four patients had vomiting as one of their symptoms, while seventy-four patients had stomach distension. Voicing grievances. Among the 100 patients, tenderness, rigidity, and lack of bowel sounds were the most frequently reported

symptoms. The distribution of additional indications and symptoms that may present, accordingly (Table 2, 3). A simple erect X-ray abdomen revealed air under the diaphragm in 86 of the 100 patients in the research, making it the most valuable radiological investigation.

Table 2: Distributions of symptoms

Signs	Duodenal perforation	%	Jejunal and ileal perforation	%
Tenderness	70	100	30	100
Distension	51	72.8	23	76.6
Guarding	65	92	28	93.3
Rigidity	58	82.8	27	90
Obliteration of liver dullness	50	71.4	18	60
Bowel sounds				
Absent	60	85.7		26 86.6
Present	10	14.3	4	13.3
Shock	18	25.7	10	33.3

Each of the 100 patients had an exploratory laparotomy as part of their surgical procedures. Figures 1, 2, and 3 show that 72 patients suffered duodenal, 23 ileal, and 7 jejunal perforations.

Figure 1: Duodenal perforation

Figure 2: Ileal perforation

Figure 3: Jejunal perforation

On a plain erect X-ray, 62 of the patients who had duodenal perforations had air under the diaphragm. Following the identification of the perforation location, different operations were carried out in accordance with the surgeons' surgical assessment and are indicated in Table 4. In eighty-seven cases, the perforation was simply closed. All patients with a duodenal hole had an omental patch applied. Two patients needed stricturoplasty in addition to a straightforward perforation closure, whereas five patients needed resection and anastomosis. Based

on the history and intraoperative results, twenty cases were given the Widal test to rule out typhoid, and eleven of them tested positive. Three edge biopsies from the perforation's HPE revealed positive TB tests. It was discovered that typhoid fever (47.8%), TB (13%), trauma (13%), iatrogenic fever (4.3%), and irrelevant (21.7%). Usually, trauma (42.8%) was the etiology of jejunal perforation; the remaining cases (57.2%) were non-specific.

Table 4: Operative procedure used with frequency

Procedure	Frequency			
	Duodenal	%	Jejunal and ileal	%
Simple closure with / without omentum	66	94.3	21	70
Resection and anastomosis	0	0	5	16.6
Simple drainage	4	5.7	2	6.6
Simple closure with stricturoplasty	0	0	2	6.6

Overall mortality in small bowel perforation was 15%, highest seen in ileal perforation (39%), followed by duodenal perforations (8.5%). Cases of ileal perforation had more post-operative complications when compared to duodenal and jejunal perforation.

Wound infection (25%) is the most common post-operative complication. Toxaemia (22%) and respiratory infections (10%) are the other common complications. Table 5 lists all the complications noted.

Table 5: List of complications with percentages

Post op complications	Duodenal perforation	%	Jejunal and ileal perforation	%
Wound infection	15	21.4	10	33.3
Burst abdomen	4	5.7	3	10
Toxemia	12	17.1	10	33.3
Respiratory	5	7.1	5	16.6
Paralytic ileus	3	4.2	2	6.6
Fecal fistula	1	1.4	6	20
Uraemia	8	11.4	9	30
Cardiac arrest	3	4.2	1	3.3
Obstruction	0	0	0	0
Hypotension	8	11.4	7	23.3
Encephalopathy	0	0	0	0

Discussion

One of the most frequent surgical emergencies that arises in Indian hospitals on a daily basis is perforation peritonitis. Young guys are typically affected in their prime, which contrasts sharply with the mean age of 45–60 years in the west. [4] Data on the various perforations are few, although in India, upper GI perforations are far more common than lower GI perforations, in contrast to the west where the opposite is true. [5,6]

The current study's 15% overall mortality rate for these patients is comparable to prior Indian research projects. [3] However, as was also shown in other research, ileal perforation cases had the highest mortality when compared to duodenal and jejunal perforations. [2, 6] This suggests that a key element in determining the case's outcome is the perforation site.

Duodenal perforations

Despite significant advancements in the conservative therapy of peptic ulcer disorders, this group of cases constitutes the majority of cases in the current study, and similar trends have been observed in other studies undertaken in India. [2]. Although the number of peptic ulcer cases resulting in perforations has decreased significantly, the number of elective surgical cases managing the condition has not decreased. [7].

According to the author of the current study, these patients had pneumoperitoneum on the X-ray and had typical symptoms of peritonitis. The outcome of the immediate procedures was favorable. Among the many techniques, the author decided to simply close the perforation and cover it with a pedicle omental patch. Numerous research demonstrate that this method yields highly satisfactory results. There is significantly fewer mortality and post-

operative complications in contrast to ileal and jejunal perforations, however these are primarily influenced by a number of variables, including age, co-morbidities, state of health prior to surgery, size of the perforation, delay in presentation, and delay in surgery. [8]

Jejunal perforation

These perforations are comparatively rare and are nonspecific. A history of trauma was connected to some. The vast majority of these individuals had symptoms of peritonitis and an extremely hazy past. The majority of the holes in the current investigation had very positive results when treated with straightforward closure.

Ileal perforations

This is the most common site of perforations, after duodenal perforations. [5]. Typhoid fever was the most frequent cause of these perforations, followed by tuberculosis. This demonstrates that infections account for the majority of ileal perforations, as the current study also found. Compared to other causes, enteric fever-related ileal perforations had a greater death rate. [5,11,12], When the perforation cannot be categorized based on clinical symptoms, gross examination, serology, culture, and other factors, the etiology is referred to as "non-specific." histological analysis of any disease state, including cancer, TB, and enteric fever. These ulcers typically affect the terminal ileum and are solitary. Submucous vascular embolism, persistent ischemia brought on by arteritis or atheromatous vascular disease, or medications such enteric coated potassium pills have all been implicated in their causes. [3]. After typhoid, these are the second most frequent cause of ileal perforation.

The third most frequent cause of ileal perforation is tuberculosis. When accompanied by perforations, abdominal TB primarily affects the ileum and is linked to strictures. Thirteen Following surgery, they received a multi-drug regimen for tuberculosis treatment. Similar to typhoid fever perforations, ileal tuberculosis-related perforations have a high fatality rate. [13]

Other than the conditions listed above, numerous studies have identified a number of additional causes of ileal perforations, including SLE, radiation enteritis, Behcet's illness, adhesions, ischemic enteritis, and Crohn's disease, which the author was not aware of. [9]

Ileal perforation therapy is challenging because of the surgical methods used. After the initial perforation repair, a variety of procedures are used, including simple closure, wedge excision or segmental resection and anastomosis, ileostomy, and side-to-side ileo-transverse anastomosis. [5,12] In the many research, they produced a range of findings. When the patient and the gut are in good

health, a straightforward closure may be considered.

Post-operative period

Post-operative problems are more common in cases of intestinal perforations. [2] The most frequent side effect in small bowel perforation instances is wound infections. [14] It has been demonstrated that laparoscopic repair of these perforations lowers the risk of wound infection. [15] Respiratory issues such as pneumonia, atelectasis, pleural effusion or ARDS, septicemia, and dyselectrolytaemia are also frequent consequences. These can be avoided and should be identified early and treated quickly. [1]

Conclusion

When it comes to the successful treatment of small bowel perforation peritonitis, a number of criteria are crucial. Higher doses of antibiotics and proper resuscitation always result in better outcomes. A significant factor in the result is the amount of time that passes between the start of symptoms and the patient's presentation to the surgeon. Since the perforation site is a reliable predictor of outcome, appropriate post-operative measures can be implemented to improve survival rates.

There isn't as much research done in this area, possibly because these situations are emergencies. Studies can be carried out, nevertheless, to determine the relationship between the time of presentation following the beginning of symptoms and the time of the surgical treatment following the onset of symptoms and the result. Research can be done to clarify the clinical range of jejunal perforation because there is a dearth of data on it. One might assess the role that laparoscopic surgery plays in managing the same.

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